

RATIONALE FOR CHOOSING THE METHOD OF DIGITAL SCANNING OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN PROSTHETICS WITH CERAMIC INLAYS

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Relevance. For many years, inlays and onlays made of various materials have been considered by dentists as one of the best methods of restoration for medium and large-area carious lesions (Christensen GJ). They have significant advantages such as durability, strength and aesthetics. Until now, prosthetics were made using a plaster model, which was used directly to create the prosthesis, or was digitally scanned to create a virtual model.

Improvements in digital imaging technologies have greatly simplified the process, increasing patient comfort, speed of procedures and ensuring high quality of restorations (Logozzo S, Zanetti EM, Franceschini G, Kilpelä A, Mäkyänen A.). In addition, the benefits of 3D digitalization include a reduction in the time required to obtain clinical impressions, which according to recent data has been reduced by 23 minutes compared to traditional impressions (Patzelt SB, Lamprinos C, Stampf S, Att W.). Intraoral scanners should not only provide good image resolution but also allow three-dimensional reproduction. Intraoral scanning can reduce possible distortions caused by traditional impression materials and allow impressions with a cavity to be obtained, reducing the amount of material required.

Purpose of the study: The aim of this study was to compare the clinical marginal fit of CAD-CAM inlays obtained using an intraoral digital impression or an additional silicone impression.

Material and research methods. We conducted a review of scientific literature over the past 10 years using the resources of scientific databases PubMed, Cyberleninka, eLIBRARY by keywords. For meta-analysis, articles containing evidence-based experimental and clinical data on the most pressing issues of ceramic inlay prosthetics were used.

Research results. The values of marginal fit of the occlusal and free surfaces depended on the type of impression. There were no differences between the surfaces (occlusal and free). The gap in the scanning group was $164 \pm 84 \mu\text{m}$, and in the traditional impression group it was $209 \pm 104 \mu\text{m}$, and the difference between them was statistically significant ($p = 0.041$). The mean values of overdistance were $60 \pm 59 \mu\text{m}$ in the digital impression group and $67 \pm 73 \mu\text{m}$ in the traditional impression group, and there was no difference between them ($p = 0.553$).

Conclusions. In this study, we can conclude that digital impressions can achieve better clinical marginal fit of inlays and onlays and can replace traditional silicone materials. In addition, the study suggests that digital impressions improve clinical outcomes and simplify the digital workflow.

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